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The Concept of Sustainable Development

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Abstract

The subject of our study focuses on clarifying the concept of sustainable development so that it is a smooth and circulating term among people and in all societies in order to reach a green sustainable environment. The philosophy of sustainable development is based on an important fact, according to which concern for the environment is the solid foundation for development in all its aspects. This type of development is the one that focuses on two important dimensions, the present and the future. present, without at the expense of future generations.

Sustainable development is based mainly on setting incentives that reduce pollution, the volume of waste and residuals, and the current consumption of energy, and sets controls that limit the wasteful consumption of water, air and other vital resources.

Key Words: *Sustainability education, early education in building a sustainable society, building sustainable awareness, problems, challenges, sustainable development*

Introduction

1968 The establishment of the Club of Rome, which brought together a large number of businessmen from different countries. The club called for the necessity of conducting research related to the areas of scientific development to determine the limits of growth in developed countries.

1972 The Club of Rome publishes a detailed report on the development of human society and its relationship to the exploitation of economic resources, and publishes its forecasts for the year 2100. etc.

1972 The Stockholm Conference on the Human Environment, organized by the United Nations, was held. The conference discussed the environment and its relationship to the reality of poverty and lack of development in the world. It was declared that poverty and lack of development are the worst enemies of the environment. On the other hand, the conference criticized countries and governments that still ignore the environment when Development planning.

1992: The Earth Summit in Rio de Janeiro, where it became clear that the world's attention should be directed not to the impact of economics on the environment, but to the impact of environmental pressure (soil erosion - water systems - atmosphere) on economic concepts.

In Rio, sustainable development focused on seven components that constitute the greatest challenge facing humanity:

Population control.

- Human Resource Development.

- Food production.
- Biodiversity.
- energy.
- manufacturing.
- urbanization.

1994 The Global Conference on the Sustainable Development of Small Island Developing States (Bridgetown, Barbados) adopts the Barbados Program of Action, which stipulates specific actions and measures for the sustainable development of Small Island Developing States.

1997 The special session of the General Assembly (Earth+5 Summit) in New York adopts the program for the further implementation of Agenda 21, including the work program of the Commission on Sustainable Development for the period 1998-2002.

2002 The World Summit on Sustainable Development in Johannesburg, South Africa: Although this summit was devoid of the birth of any new environmental agreement, it laid the groundwork and paved the way for practical measures to enable the countries of the world to implement the principles and agreements that resulted from previous global environmental conferences. Through the following points:

- Evaluation of the progress achieved in the implementation of Agenda 21 issued by the United Nations Conference on Development and the Environment in 1992.
- Reviewing the challenges and opportunities that may affect the possibilities of achieving sustainable development.

Propose the procedures to be taken and the necessary institutional and financial arrangements for their implementation.

Determining ways to support the necessary institutional building at the national, regional and international levels.

The concept of sustainable development

Before addressing the concept of sustainable development, sustainability must be uncovered as a starting point, as the origin of sustainability goes back to the science of ecology, where sustainability was used to express the formation and development of dynamic systems, which were subjected to structural changes, leading to a change in their characteristics and elements, and the relationships of these elements. to each other, and in the developmental concept, the term sustainability was used to express the nature of the relationship between economics and ecology.

Due to the novelty and generality of the concept of sustainable development, its meanings have varied in various scientific and practical fields. Some deal with this concept as an ethical vision, others as a new development model, and there are those who see that the concept is a modern idea for rich countries, which gave the concept of sustainable development a kind from ambiguity, and in order to remove this, various definitions and previous and modern points of view must be presented.

The concept of sustainable development has become widely circulated and has multiple meanings, and the problem is not in the absence of definitions, but rather in their multiplicity and different meanings.

Sustainable development: development durable is a translation that does not respond to the English term sustainable development, which can also be translated as (sustainable) or (connected) development. The term (sustainable) was chosen because it is the term that reconciles the meaning and grammatical rules.

As defined by Edwerd Barbier: "It is that activity that leads to the improvement of social welfare as much as possible, while taking care of the available natural resources and the least possible amount of damage and abuse to the environment, and this explains that sustainable development differs from development in that it is more complex and intertwined with what is economic." social and environmental.

The Portland report in 1987 defined sustainable development as follows: "Sustainable development is the process of development that meets the aspirations and needs of the present, without endangering the ability of future generations to meet their needs.

This new concept aims to improve the quality of human life, based on living within the framework of the carrying capacity or the carrying capacity of the surrounding environment. The philosophy of sustainable development is based on an important fact, that caring for the environment is the solid foundation for development in all its aspects. Two important dimensions are the present and the future, where the importance of sustainable development, according to this definition, lies in its ability to find a balance between the development requirements of the present generations, without it being at the expense of future generations.

As for the World Commission on Sustainable Development, it has defined it as: it is development that meets the needs of the present without endangering the resources of future generations. In a few places, or some years, but for the entire globe, down to the distant future.

It is this type of development that embodies the relationship between economic activity and its use of natural resources in the production process, and its reflection on the lifestyle of society, in a way that achieves good quality outputs for economic activity, and rationalizes the use of natural resources, in a way that secures their sustainability and safety, without affecting This rationalization negatively affects the lifestyle and its development.

Hence, sustainable development requires changing developmental policies, programs and activities, starting from the individual and ending with the world, passing through society.

It is noticeable that some deal with sustainable development as a new direction, commensurate with the interests of the new world order, and some see that sustainable development is an alternative development model different from the capitalist industrial model, and perhaps a way to fix the mistakes and pitfalls of this model in its relationship with the environment.

In general, we note that the human being is at the center of most of the definitions presented on sustainable development, as it includes human development that leads to improving the level of health care, education, social welfare, and combating unemployment. Today, there is recognition of human development as a cornerstone of economic development.

Through the above, it can be said that sustainable development is the development that achieves a balance between the environmental, economic, social and technological system, and contributes to achieving the maximum growth in the previous four systems, and that it does not have a side effect on the previous systems, and in essence it is based on points next:

Emphasizing the importance of optimal utilization of the potentials and resources available in the economy.

Preserving the environment by minimizing, as much as possible, the negative effects resulting from economic and social activities on the resources of the economy and the environment.

- Striving to achieve balanced economic development capable of bringing about a convergence in the living standards of the various groups.

Requirements for sustainable development

To achieve effective sustainable development requires compatibility and harmony between the following systems:

Political system: guarantees democracy in decision-making.

An economic system: it enables surplus realization and is self-reliant.

Social system: consistent with development plans and methods of implementation.

- Production system: enshrines the principle of environmental feasibility in projects.

- Technological system: enables research and finding solutions to the problems it faces.

An international system: enhances cooperation and exchange of experiences in the development project.

Administrative system: flexible and has the ability to self-correct.

- A cultural system: trained to root the environmental dimension in all life activities in general, and sustainable development in particular.

Sustainable Development Goals

Sustainable development seeks a number of goals that came through the following points:

- That sustainable development is a conscious - complex - long-term - comprehensive - and integrated process in its economic - social - political - cultural dimensions.

- Whatever the goal of man, he must preserve the environment in which he lives, so his goal must be to make fundamental changes in the infrastructure and superstructure, without harming the elements of the surrounding environment.

- This model of development enables all individuals to expand the scope of their human capabilities to the maximum extent possible, and to employ those capabilities in the best way in all fields.

- A model that protects the choices of generations not yet born, and does not deplete the natural resource base needed to support future development.

Dimensions of sustainable development:

Sustainable development is based on dimensions, the most important of which can be mentioned as follows:

Environmental dimension:

This dimension illustrates the strategies that must be available and respected in the field of industrialization, with the aim of optimal management of natural capital, instead of wasting and depleting it in an irrational way, so as not to affect the environmental balance, by controlling the use of resources and employing techniques that control the production of waste, the use of pollutants and the transportation of Society to the age of clean industries.

In order to achieve a clean industry, the United Nations offers the following steps:

- Encouraging environmentally sustainable industry under flexible plans.
- Oblige international companies to the same standards inside and outside their home countries.
- Raising awareness by all means of the losses and dangers resulting from pollution, whether direct or indirect.
- Introducing the concepts of a safe environment, and the obligation to maintain it, by the individual and society in all stages of education.

- Involving societies in the mechanism of sustainable development through the efforts of the media and culture for all.
- Encouraging environmentally clean production, through market mechanisms and tax policy.

In addition to adopting a clean industry, as previously mentioned, we see that it is useful to shed light on the concept of environmental projects: those that take into account the environmental dimension as a basic foundation for their establishment, and there are those who see that they are projects that contribute to economic development in parallel with preserving the environment and working with users and society in a way year with the aim of improving the quality of life for all parties.

But if the project is economic, we should not overlook the environmental feasibility study, which means: "Studying the mutual impact between development programs projects and the environment, with the aim of reducing or preventing negative impacts, or maximizing positive impacts."

In short, the most important elements within the environmental dimension can be mentioned, namely:

Ecosystems.

- energy.
- Biodiversity.

biological productivity.

- The ability to adapt.

Media and culture for all.

Clean industry.

Economic dimension

If the concept of sustainable development for the industrialized countries of the North is to seek a significant and continuous reduction in the consumption of energy and natural resources, and to bring about radical transformations in the prevailing lifestyles in consumption and production, and to limit the export of their industrial model to underdeveloped countries, then the view of the poor countries regarding sustainable development It means employing resources to raise the standard of living of the poorest population.

The most important points taken into account in the economic dimension can be summarized as follows:

Per capita consumption shares of natural resources.

The responsibility of developed countries for pollution and its treatment.

dependence on developing countries.

Equal distribution of resources.

Military spending.

Income disparity.

Social dimension

On the human and social level, sustainable development seeks to achieve high growth rates, while maintaining the stability of the population growth rate, so as not to impose severe pressures on natural resources, and to stop the flow of individuals to cities, through developing the level of health and education services in the countryside, and achieving The greatest degree of popular participation in development planning.

Hence, the social dimension leads us to highlight the following points:

Equal distribution.

Social mobility.

Popular participation.

- cultural diversity.

Institutional sustainability.

Population growth and distribution.

- Health, education and combating unemployment.

The technological dimension

And it means transferring the society to the age of clean industries, which use technology that cleans the environment, and produces a minimum amount of polluting and heat-trapping gases that are harmful to the ozone layer.

Technology for sustainable development can be promoted as follows:

- Developing research activities by promoting new materials technology and information and communication technology, and adopting sustainable mechanisms.

- Improving the performance of private institutions, through specific inputs based on modern technologies.

Creating new institutional patterns that include technology cities and incubators.

Enhancing capacity building in science, technology and innovation, in order to achieve the goals of sustainable development in a knowledge-based economy, especially since capacity building is the only way to enhance competitiveness, increase economic growth, create new job opportunities and fight poverty.

- Developing plans and programs that aim to transform society into an information society, so that new technologies are integrated into social and economic development plans and strategies, in parallel with achieving global goals such as the Millennium Development Goals.

The Natural Resources Report confirms that the common denominator of these economic, social, environmental and technological dimensions is that in order for development to be sustainable, the following must be taken into account:

- Not to ignore the environmental controls and determinants.

Not to lead to the destruction and depletion of natural resources.

- It leads to the development of human resources, such as combating unemployment and poverty and improving the status of women in society.

- Shifts occur in the prevailing industrial base.

Principles of sustainable development

A new environmental doctrine began to take shape at the beginning of the twenty-first century. It was adopted by the World Bank. This doctrine is based on ten basic principles:

• Set priorities carefully

The seriousness of environmental problems and the scarcity of financial resources necessitated strict setting of priorities and implementation of treatment procedures in stages.

- Take advantage of every dollar

Most environmental policies, including successful ones, were unduly costly, and cost-effectiveness began to be emphasized.

This assertion allows achieving many achievements with limited resources, which requires a multi-pronged approach, and appeals to specialists and economists in the field of the environment, to work together to determine the best ways to address the main environmental problems.

- Seizing profit opportunities for all parties

Some of the environmental gains will involve costs and trade-offs, and others can be achieved as by-products of policies designed to improve efficiency and reduce poverty, given the reduction of resources devoted to solving environmental problems, including the reduction of subsidies on the use of natural resources.

- Use market tools where possible

Market-based incentives to reduce tax damages are the best in principle and practice. For example, some developing countries impose emission and waste-flow fees, market-based fees for extraction operations.

- The economy in the use of administrative and organizational capabilities

Work must be done to implement more organized and capable policies, such as imposing taxes on fuel, or restrictions on the import of certain types of pesticides, and introducing the principle of incentives for industrial enterprises that seek to reduce environmental risks.

- Working with the private sector

The state must deal seriously and objectively with the private sector, as it is an essential element in the investment process, by encouraging environmental improvements for enterprises and establishing an (ISO) system that certifies that companies have sound systems for management and the environment.

- Full involvement of citizens

When addressing a country's environmental problems, the chances of success are much stronger if local citizens are involved. Such participation is necessary for the following reasons:

- 1- The ability of citizens at the local level to set priorities.
- 2- Members of local groups know possible solutions at the local level.
- 3- Members of local groups often work on monitoring environmental projects.
- 4- Citizen participation can help build public bases that support change.

- Employment partnership that achieves success

Governments should rely on tripartite engagements that include (the government - the private sector - civil society organizations), and work with integrated plans to address some environmental issues.

- Improving administrative performance based on efficiency and effectiveness

Skilled managers can achieve significant improvements in the environment at the lowest costs. For example, factory owners can reduce the percentage of air and dust pollution from 60% to 80% thanks to improving the organization of facilities from the inside.

- Integration of the environment from the start

When it comes to protecting the environment, prevention is definitely better than cure, and most countries are now seeking to assess damage mitigation and adopt what is known as environmental feasibility, and take into account the relative costs and benefits when designing their energy strategy, and they also make the environment an effective element in the framework Economic, financial, social and commercial policies.

References

Waheeb, Rasha Abdulrazzak. "Identification of Delay Causes in Construction Projects and Emergency Reconstruction "Iraq as a case study"." (2018).

Waheeb, Rasha A., Bjørn S. Andersen, and Rafea AL Suhili. "Using ANN in emergency reconstruction projects post disaster." *International Journal of Engineering Business Management* 12 (2020): 1847979020967835.

Waheeb, Rasha A., and Bjørn S. Andersen. "Causes of problems in post-disaster emergency re-construction projects—Iraq as a case study." *Public Works Management & Policy* 27.1 (2022): 61-97.

Waheeb, Rasha Abdulrazzak. "APP innovation to control projects risks management during crises." *EAI Endorsed Transactions on Internet of Things* 8.30 (2022).

Waheeb, Rasha A. "Strength & Conduct of Reinforced Concrete Corner Joint under Negative Moment Effect." *Journal of Architectural Environment & Structural Engineering Research* 4.4 (2021): 10-17.

Waheeb, Rasha A., et al. "Impact of Pandemic SARS COVID-19 on Different Construction Project Management: Problems and Solutions." *Public Works Management & Policy* (2022): 1087724X221113579.

Waheeb, Rasha, et al. "The prospective of Artificial Neural Network (ANN's) model application to ameliorate management of post disaster engineering projects." Available at SSRN 4208375 (2022).

Waheeb, Rasha. "Diagnoses of Delay Causes in Construction Projects During Disaster." Available at SSRN 4255634 (2022).

Waheeb, Rasha. "Sustainability of Societies Using Artificial Intelligence in Green Buildings Baghdad." Available at SSRN 4255832 (2022).

Waheeb, Rasha, et al. "Design of earthquake-resistant buildings by using reinforced concrete or steel flexible corner joints." Available at SSRN 4362461 (2023).

Waheeb, Rasha. "How to Prepare the Project Schedule?" Available at SSRN 4297325 (2022).

Waheeb, Rasha. "Quality Control of Steel in Steel Iron Product Factory System." Available at SSRN 4408235 (2023).

Waheeb, Rasha. "Using Digital Twin Technology to Improve Projects Management." Available at SSRN 4255641 (2022).

Waheeb, Rasha. "Dealing with Stabilization and Sustainability issues in Emergency Reconstruction Projects." Available at SSRN 4255645 (2022).

Waheeb, Rasha. "Successful Character of Project Manager (Presentation Slides)." Available at SSRN 4386359 (2018).

Waheeb, Rasha. "Dealing with Stabilization and Sustainability issues in Emergency Reconstruction Projects." Available at SSRN 4255645 (2022).

Waheeb, Rasha. "How to Prepare An Estimated Bill of Quantities for a Project? Iraqi House as a Case Study'Model'." Iraqi House as a Case Study'Model'(April 17, 2023) (2023).

Waheeb, Rasha. "How to Build Your House?" Available at SSRN 4432814 (2023).

Waheeb, Rasha A., and Bjørn S. Andersen. "Causes of Problems in Post-Disaster Emergency Re-Construction Projects—Iraq as a Case Study." Public Works Management & Policy 1 (2021): 37.